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Extent Of Effectiveness In The Performance Of Post Graduate Diploma In Education (PGDE) Graduates In Secondary Schools In Delta State

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ABSTRACT

This study is on assessing the extent of effectiveness in the Performance of Post Graduate Diploma in Education (PGDE) Graduates in Secondary Schools in Delta State. The main purpose of this study is to assess the extent of effectiveness in performance of graduates of PGDE in secondary schools in Delta State. Three (3) research questions and three (3) hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted in the study. The population of the study consisted of 958 public secondary school principals and 138 private secondary school principals from the 479 public secondary schools and 69 approved private secondary schools in Delta state. Sample size for the study will be two hundred and eighty seven (287) public secondary school principals and forty one (41) private secondary school principals representing 30% of the entire population of both public and private secondary school principals. These were selected through proportionate random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was questionnaire titled “Extent of Effectiveness in the Performance of Post Graduate Diploma in Education (PGDE) Graduates in secondary schools in Delta State (EPPGDEG)”. The instrument for data collection was a twenty two (22) items questionnaire. In order to determine the reliability of the instrument, the internal consistency of the instrument was computed using Cronbach Alpha. The overall reliability coefficient of the instrument was 0.82 showing that the questionnaire is reliable to be used. The data was collected and analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions and t-test to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that the extent of effectiveness of PGDE graduates in professional conduct, classroom management, manifestation of self-efficacy and collaboration with other colleagues are all to a low extent. Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made among others: Educational planners should make effective set up on increasing the duration of PGDE programme, Institutional leadership should provide regular seminar/workshop to increase academic activities and interest of PGDE students before graduation and Graduates of PGDE should be provided with follow up training.

Keywords: Performance; PGDE; Secondary Schools

INTRODUCTION

Teachers hold the important responsibilities of distributing curriculum to students and preparing them for life by improving their academic and vocational skills. So, teaching is a major profession requiring expertise, hence Uche and Augustine (2016) asserted that teachers are the building blocks of the educational system. To ensure effectiveness of teachers, the Federal Government of Nigeria (2014) in the National Policy on Education provided that all teachers shall be required to undergo training on the method and techniques of teaching. Following this, Teacher's Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN) after careful observations and inputs by a wide range of stakeholders had reached the conclusion that basic institutes of education is free to run Diploma programme to qualify teachers who do not have teaching qualification thus, the emergence of Post graduate diploma in education (PGDE).

Post graduate diploma in education is the indispensable graduate study program that can make the unqualified personnel qualified in teaching profession. In the light of this, Abdurahman, Mohammed and Khaled (2022) viewed Post graduate diploma in education as a post graduate program for holders of the Higher National Diploma (HND) and Degrees (B.A, BSc, MSc, PhD) who wish to be teachers but do not possess teaching qualification required to be registered with Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria. PGDE programme is therefore specially mapped out to train interested graduates in various fields who wish to take up teaching as a profession on child psychology, theories of learning, teaching methodology and general principles and practice of education so as to be equipped with the skills of teaching. The programme is scrutinized by the board of teachers registration council whose membership include among others, NUC, NCCE, NUT, NBTE and Nigerian Academy of Education. Many students over the years have studied courses other than education, thereby acquiring degree certificates in other disciplines.

Most of these students choose a career in teaching profession without professional teaching qualification, hence the observation of Uche and Augustine (2016) that over 60 percent of teachers in public primary and secondary schools in Nigeria are unqualified because they have no professional certificate in education. In Nigeria, reasonable preparations are made to improve teachers' professional development through the establishment of colleges of education, both at the federal and state levels. Institutes of education and faculties of education in various universities are also established to provide effective and professional teacher education programs. In such institutions, students are trained to form habits that will help them become teachers capable of shouldering responsibilities, showing initiative and being good models for their future pupils and students. This is because an incompetent teacher is a disgrace to the teaching profession. Incompetence in teaching according to Demis, Haileslasie & Dawit (2015) may be a matter of low intellectual capacity, inadequate training, and resistance to modern pedagogical methods, or poor attitude about the teaching profession and a lack of dedication to professional duties. Demis, Haileslasie & Dawit opined that the PGDE Programme is theoretical and practical and includes important aspects of teaching and learning.

The programme addresses the philosophical problems of the bases of educational practice, the diverse human settings within which teaching and learning occur, the practical process, content of teaching and the definition of the teacher's role and teaching ethics. At the end of the programme, learners should have in-depth knowledge of education and the professional requirements as well as competence to adequately teach at various levels of education including secondary schools. Interested teachers without professional teaching certificates therefore register for PGDE programme in order to acquire necessary teaching skills to be qualified to take up teaching duties at different levels of the education system (Nursery, Basic, Senior Secondary and Tertiary levels), or to assume leadership position in any education organization or agency. Some of these PGDE graduates are in secondary schools, hence the researchers interests in finding out the extent of their effectiveness as teachers in their various schools.

Effectiveness in performance can be referred to as the results of activities of an individual or organization over a given period of time or the assessment of how well a task is being done. Dejene (2020) defined teachers' effectiveness as the observable or measurable behaviour of a teacher in a particular situation usually experimental situation. This implies that the observed behavior of an individual must be measured or tested at a given period of time to determine his/her effectiveness. Effectiveness is therefore

determined by carrying out test which can either be mentally, orally or at best practically. Effectiveness in performance therefore refers to achievement in carrying out of a task, assignment or course allocated to one. In this study, effectiveness test in performance would be carried out on graduates of PGDE in their areas of assignments in secondary schools in Delta state,

Secondary school is that sector of the education pyramid that usually comes immediately after primary education. It is at this stage of education that students are prepared for the Polytechnics, Colleges of Education and Universities, (FGN, 2014). Within the framework of the New National Policy on Education, secondary education shall last for six years, broken into two distinct parts; Junior secondary and Senior secondary school, that are perfectly correlated.

The present structure of secondary education is contained in the 2014 National Policy on Education. According to FGN (2014:18), Secondary Education is “the education children receive after primary education and before tertiary stage “the broad goal of secondary education in Nigeria is to prepare the youths for useful living within the society and for higher education. The goals of secondary education in broad and specific terms are beautifully conceived and articulated but a close observation of some of the teachers who should impact knowledge on the students in order to achieve these goals leaves much to be desired. This seems to be blamed on lack of professionalism in teaching which the focus of PGDE. This study therefore intends to find out the extent of effectiveness in the performance of PGDE graduates in the various schools where they teach.

Statement of the Problem

Teachers stand out as one of the most important factors determining the quality of education in any country. There has been a general conception in Nigeria among teaching and nonteaching staff that the ability to teach with enthusiasm may be both in-born and acquired. It is further argued that a period of professional training may not make much difference as long as one has academic qualification. Hence, the public see intelligence, interest, and other personal traits as the only qualities assumed to be necessary for effective teaching. Therefore, not all practicing teachers are professionally trained, hence the emergence of Post Graduate Diploma in Education(PGDE) which is focused on training teachers to be professionals in teaching. Notwithstanding, the effect of the PGDE programme on the knowledge, attitude, behaviour and skills of graduates of PGDE seem to be in contention, especially with the notion and common criticism against the PGDE programme that it is a crash programme. Therefore there is cause to doubt its effectiveness on its graduates. It is against this backdrop that the researchers wish to assess Post graduate diploma in education (PGDE) graduates to find out the extent of their effectiveness through their performance in different secondary schools where they teach in Delta state.

Goals and Objectives

The main objective of this study is to assess the extent of effectiveness in performance of graduates of PGDE in secondary schools in Delta State. Specifically, the study will seek to:

3. Ascertain the extent of effectiveness of performance in professional conduct of PGDE graduates in secondary schools in Delta State.
4. Access the extent of effectiveness in performance of PGDE graduates in manifesting self-efficacy in secondary schools in Delta State.
5. Find out the extent of effectiveness in performance of PGDE graduates in collaborating with other colleagues in secondary schools in Delta State.

Research Questions

The following research questions will guide the study:

3. What is the extent of effectiveness of performance in professional conduct of PGDE graduates in secondary schools in Delta State?
4. What is the extent of effectiveness in performance of PGDE graduates in manifesting self-efficacy in secondary schools in Delta State.
5. What is the extent of effectiveness in performance of PGDE graduates in collaborating with other colleagues in secondary schools in Delta State.

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses will be formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance;

1. There is no significant difference between the responses of principals in public secondary schools and principals in private secondary schools on the extent of effectiveness of performance in professional conduct of PGDE graduates in secondary schools in Delta State.
2. There is no significant difference between the responses of principals in public secondary schools and principals in private secondary schools on the extent of effectiveness in performance of PGDE graduates in manifesting self-efficacy in secondary schools in Delta State.
3. There is no significant difference between the responses of principals in public secondary schools and principals in private secondary schools on the extent of effectiveness in performance of PGDE graduates in collaborating with other colleagues in secondary schools in Delta State.

METHODOLOGY

The descriptive survey research design was employed in this study. The population of the study was all the principals and vice principals (classified together as principals) in the 479 public secondary schools and 69 approved private secondary schools in Delta state. The sampling size consisted of two hundred and eighty seven (287) public and private secondary school principals representing 30% of the entire population.

The instrument for data collection was 22 items questionnaire, titled: “Extent of Effectiveness in the Performance of Post Graduate Diploma in Education (PGDE) Graduates in secondary schools in Delta State (EPPGDEG)” which is based on the research questions that guided the study. The structured questionnaire will be based on four (4) points rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE) with their normal values attached as 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively for positive item and the reverse for negative item. The instrument was validated. The internal consistency of the instrument was computed using Cronbach Alpha to analyze the data collected. Reliability coefficient was 0.82. The result indicated that the questionnaire was reliable and therefore considered appropriate for use. The data collected on the research questions was analyzed using mean and standard deviation while t-test statistics was used to test the hypotheses developed for the study at 0.05 level of significance. The result was presented below:

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

Research Question One: *What is the extent of effectiveness of performance in professional conduct of PGDE graduates in secondary schools in Delta State?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Response Ratings on the Extent of Effectiveness of Performance in Professional Conduct of PGDE Graduates in Secondary Schools in Delta State

S/N	STATEMENT	Mean	SD	Decision
	Graduates of PGDE:			
1	Are loyal to their employers	2.94	0.75	High Extent
2	Respect child right and dignity as specified in the educational law	1.81	0.83	Very Low Extent
3	Are guilty of corrupt practices in the education system	2.81	1.06	High Extent
4	Show favouritism to students for personal gain	2.82	0.98	High Extent
5	Have good moral conduct	2.28	0.93	Low Extent
6	Are committed to teaching ethics	2.26	1.05	Low Extent
7	Are role models to students	2.29	1.00	Low Extent
Grand Mean and Standard Deviation Scores		2.46	0.94	Low Extent

Table 1 presents the analysis of responses on the extent of effectiveness of PGDE graduates in professional conduct in secondary schools across Delta State. Principals in public and private secondary

schools in Delta State perceived PGDE graduates to show high levels of loyalty to their employers to a high extent ($M = 2.94$), and unfortunately, they were also seen to engage to a high extent, in corrupt practices ($M = 2.81$) and show favouritism for personal gain ($M = 2.82$). These high ratings on negative behaviours suggest lapses in ethical discipline. However, they were only rated to a low extent, in maintaining good moral conduct ($M = 2.28$), commitment to teaching ethics ($M = 2.26$), and being role models to students ($M = 2.29$). They were rated to a very low extent, in respecting child rights and dignity ($M = 1.81$). The standard deviation scores ranging between 0.75 and 1.06 indicated a close spread of Principals' views on each item. The overall (grand) mean score of 2.46 with a standard deviation of 0.94 indicates a low extent of effectiveness in professional conduct. This suggests that while PGDE graduates demonstrate some sense of loyalty, their moral and ethical behaviours are generally weak, implying a low level of professional discipline and conduct in Delta State secondary schools.

Research Question Two: *What is the extent of effectiveness in performance of PGDE graduates in manifesting self-efficacy in secondary schools in Delta State?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Response Ratings on the Extent of Effectiveness In Exhibiting Self-Efficacy of PGDE Graduates in Secondary Schools in Delta State

S/N	STATEMENT	Mean	SD	Decision
	Graduates of PGDE:			
8	Are highly committed to their work	2.27	1.07	Low Extent
9	Are not emotionally stable most of the time	2.21	1.07	Low Extent
10	Have self-confidence in their ability	2.02	0.98	Low Extent
11	Are innovative in their teaching	2.15	1.00	Low Extent
12	Have mastery of their subject areas	2.71	1.09	High Extent
13	Exhibit job satisfaction	2.08	0.97	Low Extent
14	Contribute greatly in planning and organization of school activities	2.26	1.08	Low Extent
15	Are high motivators to school administration	2.19	0.91	Low Extent
Grand Mean and Standard Deviation Scores		2.24	1.02	Low Extent

Table 2 presents mean and standard deviation response scores on the extent to which PGDE graduates demonstrate self-efficacy in their professional roles in public and private secondary schools in Delta State. Public and private secondary schools' principals generally perceived PGDE graduates as highly committed ($M = 2.27$), emotionally stable ($M = 2.21$), and showing self-confidence ($M = 2.02$) to a low extent respectively. Furthermore, PGDE graduates were rated to a low extent in innovation ($M = 2.15$), job satisfaction ($M = 2.08$), participation in school activities ($M = 2.26$), and motivating others ($M = 2.19$). Although, mastery of subject matter ($M = 2.71$) was rated to a high extent. The standard deviation response scores ranging between 0.91 and 1.08 indicated a slightly close spread of respondents' views. The grand mean of 2.24 ($SD = 1.02$) indicates a low extent of self-efficacy manifestation. This suggests that PGDE graduates do not demonstrate strong self-belief, enthusiasm, or confidence in their teaching roles as they appear less proactive, less emotionally stable, and less motivated which could affect teaching quality and learner outcomes.

Research Question Three: *What is the extent of effectiveness in performance of PGDE graduates in collaborating with other colleagues in secondary schools in Delta State?*

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation Response Ratings on is the Extent of PGDE Graduates Collaborate Effectively with Other Colleagues in Secondary Schools in Delta State

S/N	STATEMENT	Mean	SD	Decision
Graduates of PGDE:				
16	Are not good team workers	2.80	0.97	High Extent
17	Readily accept professional guidance from other teachers who are better than them	2.25	1.08	Low Extent
18	Have good relationship with other staff	2.20	0.98	Low Extent
19	Willingly accept delegation of duty	2.15	0.98	Low Extent
20	Contribute effectively in decision making	2.15	1.00	Low Extent
21	Are deficient in duties allocated to them	2.70	1.07	High Extent
22	Willingly stand in for their indisposed colleagues	2.80	1.01	High Extent
Grand Mean and Standard Deviation Scores		2.44	1.01	Low Extent

Table 3 presents the responses of public and private secondary school principals on the extent to which PGDE graduates collaborate with other colleagues in secondary schools in Delta State. PGDE graduates were rated poor teamwork (M = 2.80), and deficiency in duty performance (M = 2.70) to a high extent, while willingness of PGDE graduates to stand in for indisposed colleagues (M = 2.80), a positive but isolated trait was also rated to a high extent. In contrast, other collaborative attributes such as accepting professional guidance (M = 2.25), building good staff relationships (M = 2.20), accepting delegated duties (M = 2.15), and participating in decision-making (M = 2.15) were all rated to a low extent. Standard deviation scores ranging between 0.97 and 1.08 indicating a nearly close spread of respondents' views on each item. The grand mean of 2.44 (SD = 1.01) reflects a low extent of effectiveness in collaboration. Therefore, it can be inferred that PGDE graduates do not collaborate well with peers and superiors as they often display weak teamwork, limited openness to advice, and low commitment to collective goals, suggesting a need for improved professional socialization and collegial engagement.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference between the responses of principals in public and principals in private secondary schools on the extent of effectiveness of performance in professional conduct of PGDE graduates in Delta State.

Table 4: Independent Sample t-test of no Significant Difference between the Responses of Principals in Public and Principals in Private Secondary Schools on the Extent of Effectiveness of Performance in Professional Conduct by PGDE Graduates in Delta State

Schools	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean Difference	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper	t-cal.	df	p-value	A	Decision
Public	198	17.21	6.21								
				-.02424	-1.893	1.844	-.026	251	0.047	0.05	Sig.
Private	55	17.24	6.26								

Table 4 presents the results of an independent t-test of no significant difference between the responses of principals in public and principals in private secondary schools on the extent of effectiveness of performance in professional conduct of PGDE graduates in Delta State. The mean values between public secondary schools (n = 198, M = 17.21, SD = 6.21) and private secondary schools (n = 55, M = 7.24, SD = 6.26) were almost identical. However, the computed t-value of -0.021 with 251 degrees of freedom and (p = 0.047 < 0.05) between principals of public and private schools regarding the professional conduct of

PGDE graduates indicating that the difference between the two groups is statistically significant at the 0.05 level. The 95% confidence interval (CI) ranged from -1.893 (lower limit) to 1.844 (upper limit). Since the interval is narrow and does not include a practically large difference, the significance may be due to small variations in group perceptions rather than large mean disparities. This implies that principals from public and private schools perceive the professional conduct of PGDE graduates differently, even if their ratings appear numerically close. The significant difference suggests variability in expectations or experiences of PGDE graduates' professionalism across school types.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference between the responses of principals in public and principals in private secondary schools on the extent of effectiveness in demonstrating self-efficacy by PGDE graduates in Delta State.

Table 5: Independent Samples t-test of no Significant Difference between the Responses of Principals in Public and Principals in Private Secondary Schools on the Extent of Effectiveness in Demonstrating Self-Efficacy by PGDE Graduates in Delta State

Schools	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean Difference	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper	t-cal.	df	p-value	α	Decision
Public	198	17.88	7.89								
				-.60707	-2.199	1.754	-.506	251	0.613	0.05	Not Sig.
Private	55	18.49	7.79								

Table 5 examined the difference in perceptions of PGDE graduates' self-efficacy between public and private school principals in Delta State. The mean ratings public secondary schools (n = 198, M = 17.88, SD = 7.89) and private secondary schools (n = 55, M = 18.49, SD = 7.79) were similar with a mean difference of -0.60707, suggesting a shared view that PGDE graduates demonstrate low levels of self-efficacy across both school systems. A t-value of -0.506 with 251 degrees of freedom and (p = 0.613 > 0.05) indicating no significant difference between the perceptions of principals of public and private schools regarding PGDE graduates' self-efficacy. The 95% confidence interval ranged from -2.199 (lower limit) to 1.754 (upper limit), which includes zero. This suggests that any observed difference could be due to random sampling variation rather than a true difference in perceptions. Hence, principals from both public and private secondary schools hold similar views that PGDE graduates display low self-efficacy in their teaching roles.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant difference between the responses of principals in public and private secondary schools on the extent of effectiveness in performance of PGDE graduates in collaborating with colleagues in Delta State.

Table 6: Independent Samples t-test of no Significant Difference between the Responses of Principals in Public and Principals in Private Secondary Schools on the Extent of Effectiveness in Collaborating with Colleagues by PGDE Graduates in Delta State

Schools	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean Difference	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper	t-cal.	df	p-value	α	Decision
Public	198	17.03	6.82								
				-.04747	-2.099	2.004	-.046	251	0.964	0.05	Not Sig.
Private	55	17.07	6.89								

Table 6 analyzed whether there was a significant difference in the perception of PGDE graduates' collaboration with colleagues among public and private secondary school principals in Delta State. The mean ratings of public secondary schools (n = 198, M = 17.03, SD = 6.82) and private secondary schools

($n = 55$, $M = 17.07$, $SD = 6.89$) were similar with a negligible mean difference of -0.04747 . The results revealed a t -value of -0.046 with 251 degrees of freedom and ($p = 0.964 > 0.05$) showing no significant difference in the perceptions of principals of public and private schools regarding PGDE graduates' collaboration with colleagues. The 95% confidence interval ranged from -2.099 (lower limit) to 2.004 (upper limit). Because the interval spans zero, it implies that any slight variation between the groups is not statistically meaningful. Hence, there is no significant difference between the responses of principals in public and private secondary schools on the extent of effectiveness in performance of PGDE graduates in collaborating with colleagues in Delta State. Therefore, public and private secondary school principals do not differ in their perception that PGDE graduates exhibit low levels of teamwork and collaboration with colleagues.

DISCUSSION

The finding of the study as revealed by research question one showed that PGDE graduates exhibit limited professional discipline and ethical standards, performing at a generally low extent in their professional conduct. These findings are in line with Emmanuel, Iormough, Fiase, Achukwu. and Chia (2017) who reported that PGDE graduates seem not to have learnt enough professional competence in their short term program which limits their ability to acquire the skills relevant for teaching. The finding that PGDE graduates exhibit a low extent of professional conduct could therefore be attributed to inadequate ethical orientation during training and weak enforcement of professional standards in the school system. Many PGDE programmes in Nigerian universities emphasize theoretical foundations of education but often lack practical mentorship and character formation components. Consequently, graduates may possess the pedagogical knowledge but fail to internalize the moral and ethical dimensions of teaching. Nevertheless, Halliru, Hannatu and Yakubu. (2023) observed that through extensive engagements in PGDE over a period of two years, the graduates emerged confident in their teaching, their engagement in school, and their positive feelings about themselves clearly transformational in nature. Therefore, PDE graduates may become active in teaching development with a long period of practice after graduation.

The finding of the study on research question two revealed that PGDE graduates exhibit low self-belief, emotional stability, and motivation, which negatively affects their teaching confidence and classroom effectiveness. The finding of low self-efficacy among PGDE graduates suggests that many of them lack confidence and intrinsic motivation to perform their professional duties effectively. This may be due to inadequate practical teaching exposure during their training and poor mentoring structures in the schools where they are employed. The findings on the questions in research question three did not lend credence to Melkamu and, Abebe (2019) recommendation that PGDE holders though not so proficient in classroom methodology should acquire self confidence and emotional stability after graduation.

The finding of the study on research question three showed that PGDE graduates generally lack strong interpersonal and teamwork skills, showing a low level of professional collaboration and collegiality in the school environment. This negates Krammer, Rossmann and Gasterger (2018) submission that relationship with colleagues and other staff can make lots of differences in the working environment, goal attainment and performance of workers. The low level of collaboration among PGDE graduates with colleagues can be attributed to weak professional culture and poor communication networks within schools. Many PGDE graduates enter the teaching profession from diverse non-education backgrounds and may struggle to integrate socially into existing staff communities. Additionally, schools often lack a structured mentorship or peer collaboration system, which discourages teamwork and knowledge sharing. The finding emanating from hypothesis one revealed that principals in public and private schools differ slightly but significantly in their evaluation of PGDE graduates' professional behaviour. The significant difference between public and private school principals' perceptions of PGDE graduates' professional conduct may be due to variations in institutional culture and accountability mechanisms. Private schools often have stricter supervision, frequent appraisals, and performance-based evaluations, which may compel teachers to maintain higher ethical and professional standards. In contrast, public schools may

suffer from less stringent monitoring, political interference, and bureaucratic laxity, which can affect professional discipline.

The finding originating from hypothesis two revealed that principals from both public and private schools hold similar views that PGDE graduates display low self-efficacy in their teaching roles. The non-significant difference in perceptions of PGDE graduates' self-efficacy between public and private schools may be justified by the similar psychological and professional conditions teachers face across both settings. Inadequate incentives, poor recognition, and limited professional advancement opportunities are prevalent in both school types, which likely affect teachers' morale and self-belief. Additionally, PGDE graduates in both sectors often juggle teaching with other personal or professional commitments, especially those who view teaching as a transitional occupation.

The finding stemming from hypothesis three revealed that public and private school principals agree that PGDE graduates exhibit low levels of teamwork and collaboration with colleagues. The absence of a significant difference between public and private school principals' views on PGDE graduates' collaboration with colleagues can be attributed to the generally weak culture of professional collaboration in Nigerian schools. Whether in public or private settings, teachers often work in isolation due to heavy teaching loads, limited time for professional learning communities, and lack of institutional incentives for teamwork.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the study concluded that though PGDE programme is needed for upgrading of knowledge for non-professional teachers, the findings indicated that the extent of effectiveness of PGDE graduates in professional conduct, manifestation of self-efficacy and collaboration with other colleagues are all to a low extent. These findings suggested that PGDE graduates are "intellectually superficial and disconnected from deep issues of curriculum and learning". Therefore, they need improved competence after graduation.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the study made the following recommendations;

1. Educational planners should make effective set up on increasing the duration of PGDE programme.
2. There is a need to gather more evidence on the enhancement of students' learning, and the achievement of positive learning outcomes in PGDE programme by academic developers
3. Institutional leadership should provide regular seminar/workshop to increase academic activities and interest of PGDE students before graduation
4. Graduates of PGDE should be provided with follow up trainings through collaboration
5. Teacher Educators should participate in the selection process of PGDE trainees through preparation of instruments that can help identify suitable candidates.
6. Tertiary institutions need to consolidate support programs such as mentoring and induction to support PGDE students' professional growth.

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